

PROSPECTS OF PROMOTION OF SPORT AND BREWING IN THE POPULATION

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Abstract. *In recent years, efforts have been made to popularize physical fitness and sports, to promote healthy lifestyles among the population, to promote the physical rehabilitation of people with limited opportunities, and to ensure that the country has a decent participation in the field of sports. The main article contains a comparative analysis of the legal basis for the development of the sports industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as the physical training and reforms in the sports field.*

Key words: *youth, sport, sport school, attraction of population to sport, types of sport.*

Introduction

Today, promoting a healthy lifestyle, regularly engaging in physical activity and sports among the population, especially young people, encouraging them to organize their free time in accordance with the needs of the times, increasing the confidence of young people in their own behavior, strength and abilities through sports competitions and games. A wide-ranging work is being carried out to raise the sense of patriotism and loyalty to the country, as well as to organize the training of a talented sportsman in the youth, as well as the further development of physical training and mass sportsmanship.

Materials and analysis

Analyzing the quality of children's and adult schools on a national scale, there are 18 (6.81) in the Republic of Kazakhstan, 17 (6.43) in the Andijan region, 18 (6.81) in the Bukhoro region, 14 (6.81) in the Jizzakh region. 5.3%), 21 (7.95%) in Kashqadaryo region, 16 (6%) in Navoi region, 19 (7.19%) in Namangan region, 23 (8.71%) in Samarqand region, Surkhandaryo region 18 (6.81%), 13 (4.92%) in Sirdaryo region, 26 (9.84%) in Tashkent region, 24 (9.09%) in Fergana region, 15 (5.68%) in Khorezm region (%), the city of Tashkent consists of 22 (8.33%) (see Figure 1).

Fig. 1.

Children and teenagers's schools operating in the public sector (with interest).

There are 54 specialized sports schools for children and teenagers in our republic, and these indicators do not differ much from each other in the regions, in particular, Karakalpak Republic, Andijan, Fergana, Namangan, Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, Syrdarya, Jizak, In Surkhondaryo, Navoiy, 4 each and 7% of the republic, only in Khorezm and Kashkadarya regions, 3 each of 6% (see Figure 2).

Fig 2.

Specialized sport schools for children and teenagers.

On September 4, 2015, the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Physical Education and Sports" No. URL-394 was adopted, with the initiative and support of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 the program for the development of physical education and mass sports for the years was approved. Also, Decree No. RF-2821 dated March 9, 2017 "On the preparation of athletes of Uzbekistan for the XXXII Olympiad and Paralympic Games to be held in Tokyo (Yaponia) in 2020", dated March 5, 2018. It is specified in the Decree No. RD-5368 "On the measures of radical improvement of the state management system in the field of physical education and sports" and other normative legal documents related to this field. Their practical importance is evident in the high results achieved by the athletes of Uzbekistan and the construction of sports facilities that meet international requirements[1,2].

In 2021, more than 110,000 public sports events were organized to attract the population of the republic to mass sports, and 26.7 percent of the population was involved, and by the end of 2022, it is planned to increase this figure to 33 percent[3,4]. Also, in order to constantly involve the residents of the neighborhood in public sports, public sports competitions were held in running, streetball, mini-football, badminton, volleyball, basketball, table tennis and other sports. In the first quarter of 2022, 19 thousand 756 public sports events were organized in the republic, and about 2.8 million participants were included in these competitions[5,6].

In particular, in February of the current year, in February of the current year, in order to develop physical training and skills in the areas of duty, support and organization, a training session was held in Bostonliq district of Tashkent region, a festival on archery, kickball, badminton, mini-football, chess, snowboarding and mountain skiing was organized [7].

As mentioned, in the last three years, 118 sports complexes and 7,000 playgrounds in neighborhoods were put into use. Today, there are 3,500 mini-football, 6,000 basketball, volleyball, 663 badminton courts, and more than a thousand fitness halls [8]. "Health corridors" and bicycle paths were established in every district and city center. In the development strategy, the goal of increasing the number of people regularly engaged in physical education and sports to 33% in the next five years is set [9].

As noted, according to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 18, 2022, the obligation to brew Sport was established. One of its most important tasks is popularizing the internet among children and young people[10,11].

At the meeting, the Ministry of Sports Development, together with youth leaders in the neighborhoods, was assigned the task of recruiting 6 million healthy boys and girls to public sports events throughout the year. For this purpose, mass sports events are held starting from 10 appeals, consisting of neighborhood, district, regional and republic stages. To organize them, up to 100 million soums per region will be allocated from the "Youth Notebook" fund, and up to 1 billion soums will be allocated for awarding the winners and laureates. Young people with the best results will be selected for district and city, regional and national kicking teams.

Nowadays, all sports training facilities are shared and all important cultural events are held together. Therefore, the current planning work of sports facilities takes over the functional activity of the facilities.

In the design of educational institutions, playgrounds for children of different ages, physical training, sports and training grounds for physical training and rehabilitation should be provided. Places for the disabled in auditoriums and sports and entertainment facilities should be placed directly near the corridors leading to the evacuation exit; it is recommended to take into account the possibility of other spectators not colliding with the evacuation routes during evacuation when placing places for the disabled. The distance from the seats for the disabled in the viewing, sports and entertainment halls to the evacuation exit in case of emergency should not exceed 25m, and the width of the corridor should not be less than 1.2m. The width of the wheelchair path should not be less than 1.6 m [12].

It was emphasized that it is necessary to develop a rating of neighborhoods based on the participation of young people in public sports activities, to attach well-known trainers and sports players to the areas considered "unsatisfactory", and to develop sports. This is important for the further development of mass tourism in remote districts. Because, if we ensure the participation of

well-known coaches and players in the organization of public sports events that are lagging in remote areas, the interest of young people in sports will increase.

In conclusion, the timely implementation of the tasks envisaged in the meeting regarding the development of sports will help citizens not only to strengthen their health, but also to form a healthy lifestyle in society.

In our republic, it is important to increase and realize the creative and intellectual potential of the young generation, to form a healthy lifestyle among children and young people, and to involve them in physical education and sports. Today, our skiers have achieved high results in various competitions and are introducing Uzbekistan to the world. It is appropriate to pay special attention to the development of mass sports, especially children's sports, on a scientific basis, to the creation of its organizational foundations. In particular, in our country, the use of modern technical methods to reduce the probability of injury to young athletes is widely used in sports practice.

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